

Nonparametric efficiency and artificial intelligence techniques in higher education: a systematic literature review and bibliometric analysis

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Summary

1. This policy brief summarizes the first comprehensive review of how nonparametric efficiency methods and artificial intelligence (AI) techniques are applied in higher education.
 2. It finds a well-established tradition of using efficiency tools to assess university performance.
 3. AI applications in this field are growing but remain limited and underexplored.
 4. Most research focuses on a few countries, leaving major geographic gaps, particularly in Eastern Europe.
 5. We highlight significant opportunities for integrating AI into efficiency analysis to better support policymaking and institutional improvement
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1. Introduction

Higher education institutions (HEIs) are under increasing pressure to deliver high-quality outcomes despite facing financial constraints and rising global competition (Herberholz and Wigger, 2021). In this challenging environment, enhancing efficiency is essential. Artificial Intelligence (AI), with its rapid advancements and potential to perform complex tasks, has emerged as a promising tool for boosting operational effectiveness. In Dipierro et al. (2025), we explore how AI and nonparametric efficiency techniques have been applied to higher education, identifying synergies and gaps within this intersection.

Despite the proliferation of research on AI and on efficiency, an integrated perspective that jointly considers both strands in the context of HEIs has been lacking. We address that gap by conducting a comprehensive systematic literature review, guided by PRISMA methodology, and enriched by a bibliometric analysis. We examine a vast body of literature to uncover how efficiency in higher education has been assessed using nonparametric methods and how AI is increasingly being incorporated into these evaluations.

2. Data and Methodology

We conducted a structured literature review in March 2025 using the PRISMA protocol (Page et al., 2021), supported by the snowball method (Wohlin, 2014) to ensure comprehensive coverage. The search spanned three streams: nonparametric efficiency (Eff), artificial intelligence (AI), and their intersection (Eff+AI). They used the Scopus database to identify peer-reviewed journal articles published between 1978 and 2025 in English.

For the Eff stream, studies applying nonparametric techniques like Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA), Free Disposal Hull (FDH), Malmquist index, order-m, order-alpha, network, slack-based and conditional efficiency models were selected. For the AI stream, the search covered AI subfields such as machine learning, deep learning, natural language processing, and neural networks. The combination stream identified papers applying both AI and nonparametric efficiency techniques to HEIs.

The initial search yielded 639 records for efficiency, 255 for AI, and 55 for the intersection. After screening and full-text assessments, the final sample included 179 studies on nonparametric efficiency, 114 on AI, and 17 on their combination. Bibliometric analysis using VOSviewer provided insights into trends, geographic distribution, key authors, and keyword co-occurrence. Content analysis was employed to classify studies by model types, input-output configurations, scope, and methodological rigor.

This two-pronged methodology allowed us to map the academic landscape, assess evolution over time, and uncover methodological and geographic gaps in the literature.

3. Results

The review uncovers a rich and evolving body of research applying nonparametric efficiency techniques to higher education. Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) is the dominant method, used in over half of the 179 efficiency studies. Most papers adopt an output-oriented approach under variable returns to scale, reflecting the real-world constraints faced by public HEIs. Recent years have seen the emergence of more advanced methods, such as network DEA and conditional models,

signaling a shift toward more refined analytical tools.

Geographically, China, Italy, the UK, Spain and the US dominate in terms of authorship, and sample coverage. However, large gaps remain: Eastern Europe and Africa are underrepresented. Most studies focus on a single country, limiting generalizability. Sample sizes also vary widely, and while a few cross-national studies exist, they remain the exception.

The keywords analysis reveals clusters aligned with the core missions of HEIs—teaching, research, and knowledge transfer. “Efficiency,” “DEA,” and “higher education” are the most frequently used terms. The most common inputs are academic staff and funding, while outputs include number of graduates, research publications, and student employability.

Only 17 studies explore the intersection of AI and efficiency, indicating an emerging but still nascent field. These papers mainly apply machine learning to predict efficiency scores or to assist in university rankings. However, they often lack the robustness of traditional efficiency models, underscoring the need for methodological integration.

Overall, the findings show strong potential for AI to enhance efficiency evaluation, especially in managing complexity and data heterogeneity. Yet, institutional applications remain scattered, calling for a more systematic and policy-oriented research agenda.

4. Policy Recommendations

To enhance the efficiency of higher education institutions (HEIs), coordinated efforts are needed across different governance levels—within universities, at the national level, and

by supra-national authorities. This review identifies clear directions for each stakeholder group to act upon.

At the university level, university administrators should invest in internal capacity to understand and apply both nonparametric efficiency tools and AI methods. HEIs should establish dedicated teams or units responsible for monitoring institutional performance using advanced analytics. This requires building internal expertise through staff training and the recruitment of data analysts. Additionally, HEIs should develop comprehensive data systems that record academic, administrative, and financial data in a structured format, enabling accurate performance evaluation. HEIs must also foster a culture of continuous improvement by using efficiency insights to inform strategic decisions and operational reforms.

At the national level, governments and education ministries should play a central role in promoting methodological innovation and ensuring equitable research coverage. Funding should prioritize projects that integrate AI and advanced efficiency techniques, especially those with practical policy applications. Policymakers should support the development of national education data repositories that standardize input and output indicators across HEIs, facilitating comparative benchmarking. Additionally, national quality assurance frameworks can incorporate efficiency metrics, encouraging institutions to align their practices with measurable performance standards. Countries should also address regional disparities by supporting research on efficiency in less-represented areas and enabling small or resource-constrained institutions to benefit from performance-enhancing technologies.

At the supra-national level, organizations such as the European Commission and international research networks should invest in cross-country studies to support knowledge transfer and policy learning across borders. These bodies can play a pivotal role in funding collaborative projects that unite researchers, policymakers, and institutions from multiple countries. By promoting common data standards and shared platforms, they can reduce fragmentation and foster robust comparative research. Supra-national authorities should also provide guidance and training programs for policymakers and institutional leaders on how to use AI and efficiency analysis for system-wide improvement. Ultimately, these coordinated efforts can help create a more efficient, data-informed, and equitable higher education landscape across regions.

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